

LUNAR MANTLE RELICTS IN A 4.1-BILLION-YEAR-OLD CHANG'E 6 BASALT. K. Zhao^{1,2}, Y. L. Xue^{1,3}, H. Hui^{1,4,5*}, Y. T. Gu^{6,7}, W. X. Ouyang¹, Z. Y. Han¹, Y. Zhang¹, Y. T. Lin¹, K. X. Xu¹, H. Hu¹, J. Y. Ding¹, Q. L. Li⁵, T. Y. Yang¹, G. Zeng¹, X. C. Lu^{1,8}, R. C. Wang^{1,8}, ¹State Key Laboratory for Mineral Deposits Research & Lunar and Planetary Science Institute, School of Earth Sciences and Engineering, Nanjing University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210023, China (hhui@nju.edu.cn), ²CAS Key Laboratory of Planetary Sciences, Purple Mountain Observatory, Chinese Academy of Science, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210023, China, ³Key Laboratory of Gemological Design and Testing, School of Jewelry and Art Design, Wuzhou University, Wuzhou, Guangxi, 543002, China, ⁴CAS Center for Excellence in Comparative Planetology, Hefei, Anhui, 230036, China, ⁵Key Laboratory of Earth and Planetary Physics, Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, 100029, China, ⁶School of Geography and Ocean Science, Nanjing University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210023, China, ⁷School of Resource and Environment, Henan University of Engineering, Zhengzhou, Henan, 451191, China, ⁸Frontiers Science Center for Critical Earth Material Cycling, Nanjing University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210023, China.

Introduction: The lunar mantle, derived from the magma ocean and positioned between lunar crust and core, is fundamental to unravel the formation and evolution history of the Moon [1]. However, no definitive mantle materials have been confirmed in the lunar sample collection to date [2]. The South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin is the largest impact structure on the Moon, and materials transported by the SPA forming impact could contain some deep lunar materials. China's Chang'e 6 (CE6) mission successfully returned regolith samples from the Apollo crater within the SPA basin. These samples thus provide an unprecedented opportunity to discover mantle materials.

Mantle materials may be excavated by large meteorite impacts or transported to the lunar surface by volcanic eruptions [3]. The crust underneath Apollo crater could be as thin as <5 km. Therefore, volcanic eruptions within Apollo crater could have transported mantle materials to the surface before these mantle materials were dissolved in the magma. We present a unique CE6 basaltic clast (G06, 500×600 micrometers), containing highly magnesian olivine and orthopyroxene with a texture distinct from typical basaltic clasts (Fig. 1a). This clast may afford a piece of the farside mantle to unravel the early evolution of the Moon.

Pristine high-alumina basalt clast: Clast G06 exhibits a porphyritic texture, comprising ~10 vol% euhedral-subhedral phenocrysts and ~85 vol% ophitic-subophitic matrix (Fig. 1a). The phenocryst assemblage consists of orthopyroxene (Mg# = 65–78, where Mg# is molar ratio of Mg/(Mg+Fe)×100), clinopyroxene (Mg# = 51–67), and plagioclase (An = 88–97, where An is molar ratio of Ca/(Ca+Na+K)×100). The matrix is dominantly composed of clinopyroxene (Mg# = 56–66) and plagioclase (An = 87–92). Major element compositions of phenocryst and matrix are largely overlapped and share similar variation trends,

suggesting that they crystallized from a common parental melt. In addition, a small number (~5 vol%) of high-Mg (Mg# = 84) olivine and orthopyroxene crystals (30–60 μm) are present in the clast. Distinct from the phenocrysts in clast G06, these high-Mg olivine and orthopyroxene crystals are surrounded by clinopyroxene (Mg# = 62–70) overgrowths (Fig. 1b-d).

Fig. 1 Back-scattered electron images of clast G06. Ol, olivine; Opx, orthopyroxene; Cpx, clinopyroxene; Pl, plagioclase; Spl, spinel.

The bulk Al₂O₃ content of clast G06 has been determined to be ~16 wt%, defining this clast as a high-Al basalt. Ratio of La and Cr, contents of siderophile elements (such as Ni and Co), and pattern of rare earth elements (REEs) of clast G06 resemble those of pristine Apollo 14 high-Al basalts but differ from those of impact melts. Furthermore, strong and sharp Raman peaks of plagioclase, pyroxene, and olivine in clast G06 indicate that shock metamorphism on this clast could be minimal. These lines of evidence collectively suggest that this high-Al basaltic clast G06 is pristine.

The phenocrysts in clast G06 present as fragments and lack any preferred orientation, different from the phenocrysts that formed in lava flow. This difference indicates that clast G06 may represent a basaltic pyroclast, composed of crystal

fragments that were welded by fast cooling melt. The crystal fragments were brought to the surface by an explosive volcanic eruption. This eruption could have occurred at 4106 ± 47 Ma, a precise lead-lead age of clast G06, determined using a secondary ion mass spectrometer.

Lunar mantle residual minerals: The high-Mg olivine crystals in clast G06 show normally zoned Mg# profile but has nearly constant aluminum contents within each grain. The decoupling of Mg# and aluminum profiles in olivine suggests that the normal zoning of Mg# has mostly resulted from Fe-Mg interdiffusion in olivine. This interdiffusion could have been driven by the interaction between the high-Mg olivine crystals and their surrounding melts. This crystal-melt interaction is consistent with the resorption rims observed around these olivine crystals, which show partially developed sawtooth-like crystal surfaces joined by smoothly curved or rounded surfaces (Fig. 1b, c). Furthermore, the homogeneous Al distribution within each high-Mg olivine grain indicate the absence of magmatic growth zoning, further suggesting that the high-Mg olivine in clast G06 did not crystallize directly from the host basaltic melts.

No Al_2O_3 zoning was observed in the high-Mg orthopyroxene, similar to that in the high-Mg olivine. The resorption rims and clinopyroxene overgrowths suggest the development of reaction rims surrounding the high-Mg orthopyroxene. More importantly, REE contents in the high-Mg orthopyroxene crystals are much higher than those in the orthopyroxene phenocrysts. The high-Mg orthopyroxene REE contents are also higher than those in the orthopyroxene equilibrated with the matrix, as estimated using partition coefficients determined from crystal lattice strain model. This difference in REE abundances demonstrates that the high-Mg orthopyroxene crystals are not crystallization products of the host basaltic melt.

Siderophile and incompatible element ratios in olivine (e.g., Ti/V, Cr/Y, Ti/Cr, and Al/Cr) suggest that the trace element compositions of high-Mg olivine in clast G06 do not fall within the compositional fields of high-Mg olivine in impact melts and Mg-suites. This compositional difference indicates that the high-Mg olivine crystals in clast G06 were not likely captured from crustal lithologies during magma eruption. Moreover, REE distribution pattern of the high-Mg orthopyroxene in clast G06 differs from that of Mg-suite orthopyroxene. Therefore, the high-Mg orthopyroxene crystals in clast G06 do not likely represent crustal xenocrysts. In conclusion, the high-Mg olivine and orthopyroxene in clast G06 could not have originated from the lunar crust.

The bulk melt of clast G06, with an Mg# of ~ 62 is in equilibrium with the high-Mg olivine and

orthopyroxene cores (Mg# = 84). This equilibrium points to a plausible scenario that the high-Mg olivine and orthopyroxene may represent partial melting residues of mantle source of clast G06. The equilibrium pairs of olivine core-melt and orthopyroxene core-melt allow to estimate the temperature and pressure of partial melting in the lunar mantle source. The partial melting was estimated to have occurred at 1289 ± 45 °C (1281 ± 26 °C) and 0.90 ± 0.29 GPa using a combination of olivine-melt thermometer (orthopyroxene-melt thermometer) and melt silica activity barometer. These estimates are consistent with temperature of $>1230 \pm 26$ °C and pressure of $>0.50 \pm 0.25$ GPa, using Ca-in-orthopyroxene thermometer and Al-in-orthopyroxene barometer. This pressure corresponds to a depth of 170 ± 50 km in the Moon, which represents the upper mantle condition. These estimates are also consistent with the P-T condition ($\sim 1330 \pm 20$ °C and $\sim 1.0 \pm 0.1$ GPa) of multiple saturation point (MSP) using pMELTS program. This MSP could have occurred at a depth of 190 ± 20 km. This calculated partial melting depth is consistent with the MSP conditions reported for Apollo mare basalts. Therefore, the high-Mg olivine and orthopyroxene in clast G06 likely represent the lunar mantle at depths of 170–190 km.

Nature of lunar mantle at 4.1 Ga: The REE enrichment observed in high-Mg orthopyroxene demonstrates that these mantle minerals could have been metasomatized by a KREEP-rich melt. Furthermore, the REE distribution pattern in this matrix is parallel to that of KREEP. The high μ value ($\mu = 1830 \pm 30$) also suggests that the mantle source of clast G06 is enriched in KREEP. Moreover, the age of high-Al basalt clast G06 (4106 ± 47 Ma) is similar to that of Apollo 14 Group B high-Al basalts (4040 ± 60 Ma), and the incompatible trace element ratios of this high-Al basalt clast also resemble those of Apollo 14 Group B high-Al basalts. The mantle source of this Apollo 14 high-Al basalt group has been interpreted to have experienced KREEP metasomatism. Therefore, the farside mantle represented by high-Mg olivine and orthopyroxene in clast G06 could have been metasomatized before partial melting. This metasomatism demonstrates that KREEP must have migrated downward into the deep mantle. KREEP was likely distributed globally, supporting the existence of a magma ocean on the early Moon.

References: [1] Moriarty D. P. et al. (2021) *Nat. Commun.* 12, 4659. [2] Treiman A. H. and Semprich, J. A (2023) *Am. Mineral.* 108, 2182-2192. [3] Shearer, C. K. et al. (2015) *Meteoritics & Planet. Sci.* 50, 1449-1467.